

THE MAIN METHODS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10598147>

Annotation: This article discusses the characteristics of the methods and methods of developing creative thinking of primary school students in the educational process. Discussions of researchers-scientists on the development of creative thinking are also presented.

Key words: cognitive activity, creativity, problem-based learning, observation, comparison, analysis, motivation.

Introduction.

Creative thinking develops when students are faced with learning problems that do not have ready-made models for solving them and are not given instructions on how to solve them: in such a situation, students' teacher-directed search perform their activities, independently solve educational problems, acquire knowledge.

The process of acquiring knowledge and skills in the conditions of problem-based education covers not only the intellectual, but also the sphere of emotional and volitional personality, education for children becomes more joyful and interesting.

Analyzing psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature, determining the current state of problematic education in the primary grades of the school, allowed us to come to the conclusion that the issues of problematic education are not creatively developed for young people at the educational stage and are not resolved in the practice of primary grades. .

The researches of didactics specialists, psychologists and pedagogues have shown that the purposeful and specially organized development of creative thinking of students is the main condition for the successful organization of a highly effective educational process. In educational practice, the fact that a high level of cognitive creative activity of children has a positive effect on the entire educational process is not yet sufficiently taken into account. There was a need to develop a system of teaching methods and forms that contribute to the development of students' creative thinking.

The driving forces of the educational process are the more complex didactic and methodological tasks put forward in the process of learning a certain educational subject and the level of knowledge, skills, abilities, and the level of independent thinking of the student. contradictions between Constantly correcting the methodical strategy of the teacher in connection with the improvement of the students' learning skills and the consistent complexity of the tasks of learning the academic discipline has deep meaning and great prospects. The teacher must constantly diagnose the level of learning of students, that is, it is necessary to carefully look at what qualitative changes are taking place in educational activities, the work of the mind from semester to year. This allows him to organize the process in time, make it more dynamic and alive.

Motives of educational work play an important role in the nature of the student's psychological image, they directly affect the specific characteristics of their activity and its final results. Motives represent the inner, need-based, motivating reason for learning. There are two groups of motifs:

- *social (desire to have a good profession, benefit society, etc.);*
- *motivations related to educational activities, cognitive interests.*

Social motives create favorable conditions for the implementation of the doctrine, since it is not possible to build it only by creating interest. But the predominance of generalized social stimuli loses its appeal. Therefore, social motives should be combined with the formation of a positive emotional attitude to classes in students. In the educational process, it is important to regularly educate students' desire for knowledge, the desire to fully cover the studied area, to acquire reasonable skills of educational work. If the teacher successfully solves this problem, then cognitive interest is the winner of the work of intensive thinking and emotional elevation in teaching. An important means of encouraging it is the proper organization of the educational process and, first of all, relying on the independence of the students' knowledge.

A decrease in positive attitude towards learning is not an indicator of a decrease in cognitive interests. On the contrary, children come to school with a clear interest in the surrounding reality and learning. Attitudes to lessons change due to significant methodological miscalculations. Cognitive processes in elementary school students regularly change: perception becomes more stable and deeper, memory becomes logical, arbitrary understanding and abstract thinking improve. However, teachers do not take all of this into account.

Teachers, psychologists (*D. N. Bogoyavlenskiy, E. Y. Golanta, V. V. Davydova, B. P. Esipova, S. V. Juikova, E. I. Kabanova-Meller*)¹ Researches conducted on the basis of materials of various educational subjects skillfully organized educational activities have a beneficial effect on the cognitive interests of elementary school students. The positive motivation of education, in turn, helps to master the program material more deeply and to form strong personal creative qualities of students.

It is time to activate the teacher with such instructions that help to develop the creative thinking of the students. Existing textbooks do not meet this requirement. They do not contain various didactic materials for observations, little algorithmic instructions are given to help guide children's thoughts in the process of analyzing the studied facts and events. Although there are modern textbooks and pedagogical manuals, they cannot replace meaningful training manuals aimed at the teacher. If the teacher constantly puts the student in the position of a researcher, then all the topics studied will be received with interest in positive emotional and intellectual conditions.

The role of the educational process in the education of creativity of elementary school students. Today, researchers of creativity focus on the problem of connection between intellectual abilities, intellectual activity and creative qualities of a person, his creative thinking. Among foreign scientists studying this problem *D. Gilford*², *D. Jonson, M. Vogel, D.*

¹ Е.С. Немкина // Начальная школа с вкладкой Практика [Текст]: журнал. — 2014. — №8. — С. 71.

² Гилфорд. Д. Три стороны интеллекта // Психология мышления / Ред. А. М. Матюшкин. — М.: Прогресс, 1965.-525 с.-С. 456.

Goven, K. Kollel, T. Domino and there are others, for many years scientists believed that the higher the level of mental ability, the more creative a person should be. However, experiments have shown that these two indicators are not related to each other: "weak connections appear between creative achievements and disadvantages (intelligence coefficient) or they do not appear at all" (*J Guilford*). Scientists associate this phenomenon with significant shortcomings of modern education both at school and in higher education. Its main drawback is the lack of development and intellectual impact on students' creative thinking. Often students are engaged in real creativity outside of school.

Many foreign scientists (*S. Parne, A. Osborn, A. Kestler, B. Olmo, J. Guilford*) emphasize that creative thinking should be developed in a person who studied at school. It is necessary to constantly look for such effective methods that encourage the student to actively think creatively, make him flexible in his judgments and imaginations, influence the creation of ideas, search for alternative judgments, etc. Thus, in many cases there is an opinion that the development and implementation of developing teaching methods is very important for the socio-economic development of the country. The merits of French pedagogy can be considered the successful development and implementation of methods for developing students' creative thinking (*A. Bodeau, J. Burre, J. Druel, A. Drewel, A. Mol*). In their works, methods of developing creative thinking such as brainstorming method, synectics, pedagogical games, conferences, etc. are considered. The development of other methods of developing creative abilities by early introduction of students to scientific research is being actively carried out. At the same time, special attention is paid to heuristic methods, which are often called creative methods.

The educational process is an alternative means of developing students' creative thinking, that is, individual psychological characteristics of a person that ensure the success of his effective educational and cognitive heuristic activities.

Psychological science, as we mentioned above, denies the uniqueness of a person's abilities and the level of his knowledge, skills and abilities. Creative abilities are defined, manifested only in active and productive activities. For example, it is impossible to assess the student's ability to literary creativity, if he does not yet have the appropriate skills to work on the figurative word. Only in the process of literary creation can one make a conclusion about whether he has the appropriate abilities. It is not possible to conclude that the student lacks abilities because he has not discovered certain knowledge.

The level of knowledge of ancient Greek scientists was not high enough, but their works had a significant impact on the further development of science. It is very well expressed in the following words of the 17th century German scientist G. K. Lichtenberg: "the ancient people were superior to us in terms of creativity because they did not know dogmatism, they did not imitate anyone, they observed nature more, they learned more things than words. they were freer, they didn't write to earn a piece of bread"³.

Creativity is manifested not in knowledge, skills and abilities, but in the dynamics of their acquisition and use in non-standard practical activities. The impact of development on a person is only effective knowledge.

³ Леонтьев А.Н. Деятельность. Сознание. Личность. - М.: Политиздат, - 1975. - 304 с.

The need for creative activity is one of the most necessary and unchanging human needs. Creativity, in fact, is the main condition for the true happiness of every person. In addition, the combination of different abilities has a significant impact on the results of creative activity. This reveals an important aspect of a person's creative abilities for teachers, for example, the compensation of some characteristics by others, the person works stubbornly and persistently.

Thus, creativity is a sum of mental properties. Among them, there is a general group of qualities that meet the requirements of not one, but many types of creative activity, artistic, scientific, construction, etc., in which the following types can be named:

- *ability to see the problem;*
- *carrying out research activities;*
- *forming hypotheses, determining the topic of research;*
- *choosing adequate research methods, conducting experiments, summarizing.*

There are special qualities that meet the requirements of certain creative activities. Knowing the general and special qualities of a creative person is very important for the teacher, because it is designed to create favorable psychological and pedagogical conditions for their development.

The highest stage of skill development is usually called talent. Talent is a combination of different abilities that gives a person the ability to do complex creative work independently and in a unique way. Any ability taken separately does not serve as an analogue of talent, even if it is most clearly expressed. This is particularly the case with studies of people with phenomenal memory. In this memory feature, many are ready to see the equivalent of talent.

In the process of studying gifted children, under the influence of teachers, important qualities of a successfully developing creative person are identified: interest in creativity, carefulness, gradual preparation for hard work. As a result, important qualities of intellectual work, such as the speed of thought processes, flexibility of mind, distinguishing important things, sufficient learning, etc., are formed from a young age, and the mental state of inspiration begins to play an important role in the child. This has long been considered an indispensable quality of talent. However, there is no reason to pit inspiration against hard work with creativity, because it is work that forms its basis.

Conclusion.

Thus, the most reliable way to develop creative abilities is to diagnose them in time and introduce students to intensive informal creative activities very early. Based on the work of local researchers, we can say that primary school age is a favorable period for identifying and developing a person's creative thinking, because at this age the foundations of a creative and educational trajectory, the psychological foundations of production activity are laid, a complex begins to form, a person's creative attitude to reality underlying qualities, values, abilities and needs.

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